

Investigating Sequential Item Effects in a Testlet Model

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Abstract

Scenario-based assessments are well-suited for measuring professional decision-making skills such as clinical judgment. However, these types of items present a unique challenge to a testlet-based model because of potential sequential item effects. This research investigates the impact of sequential item effects within a testlet model.

Investigating Sequential Item Effects in a Testlet Model

For measurement professionals, drawing valid inferences from scores on assessments is a paramount concern. Substantiating valid inferences can be challenging, especially for assessing higher-order thinking skills. Clinical judgment, for example, is often assessed through scenario-based items. Clinical scenarios nest interrelated items, but the sharing of a common stimulus causes issues for score validation. The issue of nested items has a similar expression in the area of reading comprehension, where several items share the same reading passage. Because a number of factors impact reading comprehension, deriving ability estimates under a model that does not account for the effects of a common stimulus promotes inappropriate inferences (cf. Tobias, 1994).

Bradlow, Wainer, and Wang (1999) developed a testlet model as a way to handle these types of issues, which was extended and re-expressed by Li, Bolt, and Fu (2006) as equivalent to the bifactor model (Bock, Gibbons, & Muraki, 1988). A random effect for each testlet extracts the residual influence of attributes associated with the common stimulus. Consequently, item responses are conditionally independent, and their parameters are estimated without bias. The expression of the general model (hereafter referred to as GT) is

$$P(y_{ij} = 1) = \Phi(\alpha_{i1}\theta_j - t_i + \alpha_{i2}\gamma_{d(i)j}), \quad (1)$$

which, for each item, estimates a single threshold (t_i) and two loadings (α_{i1} & α_{i2}) on two dimensions, an overall ability (θ_j) for examinee j and a testlet effect ($\gamma_{d(i)j}$) for testlet $d(i)$. As an illustration, Figure 1 displays responding probabilities for two equal-ability examinees across three testlets. The black asterisk represents the responding probabilities when the testlet effect is omitted. As made apparent, the probabilities across the entire testlet are shifted per each examinee, with a large shift in Testlet A and a modest shift in Testlet C.

Figure 1. Probability of correct response under the General Testlet model for two examinees across three different testlets. The asterisk indicates the responding probabilities when omitting item dependencies.

However, assessments of decision-making for some domains cannot avoid inter-item dependencies within testlets. Busemeyer and colleagues showed that observations assessing decision-making are sensitive to another type of dependency, which is sequential in nature (Busemeyer, Pothos, Franco, & Trueblood, 2011; Atmanspacher & Roemer, 2012). This suggests inter-item dependencies cannot be modeled as a simple uniform shift—which the testlet model implies. Thus, even after extracting the testlet random factor, item responses are not considered conditionally independent. Unfortunately, scenario-based testlets are well-suited for measuring decision-making because they facilitate assessment of the decision outcome and the mental process involved with making the decision. This is important because clinicians can produce positive outcomes by following incorrect mental models of the problem. This poses risk issues for the public: Lucky outcomes cannot be the basis for claims of competence. Therefore, it is vital to determine whether the correct mental process underlies the correct outcome.

Because mental processes are especially sensitive to sequencing effects, item order is critically important (Atmanspacher & Roemer, 2012). Assessing decision-making is accomplished by developing items that move through the elements of a cognitive processing model, which breaks down a complex process into essential and manageable components. For example, Thomas, Dougherty, Sprenger, and Harbison (2008) break down decision-making into the processes of 1) recognizing pertinent information, 2) generating hypotheses that explain observations, and 3) evaluating hypotheses to select the most viable.

Although theoretically driven models simplify assessment, they do not prevent unintended consequences of measuring mental processes (Busemeyer et al., 2011), e.g. a set of options or content for one element in the scenario could bring attention to information examinees would not and did not otherwise consider. Furthermore, items in a scenario have a natural sequential progression, and therefore, examinees cannot go back and alter responses to previous items. Because of this, any subsequent information that alters an examinee's mental model will also alter responding behavior for ensuing items that assess decision-making.

Two different types of sequential effects are likely, one linear and one exponential (Lange, Thomas, & Davelaar, 2012). A linear effect of item sequence occurs when a scenario's items gradually provide revelation into the decision task: item responses become dependent upon each other. Empirically, this increases the probability that one entertains the correct hypotheses, endorses the correct hypothesis, and reaches the correct clinical decision. However, revelation does not occur at the same rate for all and is thus best modeled as a zero-centered random effect of item serial position (Random Linear Testlet; RLT). The structural form of this model is

$$P(y_{ij} = 1) = \Phi(\alpha_{i1}\theta_j - t_i + sp_{d(i)}\delta_{d(i)j}), \quad (2)$$

with $sp_{d(i)}$ taking on the serial position of item i in testlet d (e.g., 0, 1, 2 for a three-item testlet) and $\delta_{d(i)j}$ representing the slope of the sequential effect, which is assumed to have a $N(0, \sigma_{\delta_{d(i)j}}^2)$ distribution. To show how responding probabilities differ as a function of testlet serial position, Figure 2 displays the responding probabilities for equal-ability examinees across three testlets, with asterisks representing

responding probabilities when the sequential testlet effect omitted. As the two examinees progress through the testlet, their responding probabilities diverge. The responding probability for Examinee A increases linear whereas the probability decreases for Examinee B.

Figure 2. Probability of correct response under the Random Linear Testlet model for two examinees across three different testlets. The asterisk indicates the responding probabilities when omitting item dependencies.

In contrast to a linear testlet effect, an exponential effect of item sequence occurs when revelation happens more rapidly and then tapers off. In the context of decision-making, for example, an examinee can develop an incorrect hypothesis when viewing initial information presented in a scenario. Then, information contained in a following item draws attention to an otherwise neglected, but valid, hypothesis. This increases correct responding for all following items. This type of revelation happens for some, but not all, examinees and is thus best described as a mixture model (Mixture Exponential Testlet; MET). This model introduces a latent indicator defined as

$$C_j = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if examinee shows no revelation} \\ 1 & \text{if examinee shows revelation} \end{cases}$$

such that when $C_j = 0$, response probabilities follow the standard 2PL item response model,

$$P(y_{ij} = 1 | C_j = 0) = \Phi(\alpha_{i1}\theta_j - t_i), \tag{3}$$

and when $C_j = 1$, response probabilities are augmented by a shifted exponential function that results in negatively accelerating probabilities,

$$P(y_{ij} = 1 | C_j = 1) = \Phi(\alpha_{i1}\theta_j - t_i + (\omega_{d(i)j} - \omega_{d(i)j}^{1/sp_{d(i)}})). \tag{4}$$

The new term in the MET model ($\omega_{d(i)j} - \omega_{d(i)j}^{1/sp_{d(i)}}$) is parsimonious in that a single parameter captures a nonlinear trend that is shifted to begin on the second item in a testlet. Across three testlets, Figure 3 demonstrates how responding probabilities for equal-ability examinees differ, with asterisks representing responding probabilities when the sequential testlet effect omitted (which is equivalent to $C_j = 0$).

Figure 3. Probability of correct response under the Mixture Exponential Testlet model for two examinees across three different testlets. The asterisk indicates the responding probabilities when omitting item dependencies.

The model is similar to the RLT in that 1) it explains sequential dependencies within a testlet and 2) assumes that responding probabilities do not differ for a testlet's first item. Conversely, it differs from the RLT in that divergencies in responding probabilities do not substantially increase as examinees progress through testlet items. Instead, the MET assumes that revelation occurs rapidly and then tapers off, materializing spiked responding probabilities.

The current paper begins a line of inquiry into the effects of sequential item dependencies within a testlet model. Because all three models are highly similar, the paper explores the power required for a model to capture its data and whether its fit to the data is substantially better than the other models. Taking a simulation approach, we compare the two sequential testlet models (RLT & MET) above to that of Li et al. (2006; GT) and factorially manipulate the following variables:

1. the true model (GT Model, RLT Model, MET Model);
2. the fitted model (GT Model, RLT Model, MET Model);
3. the number of testlets (6, 8, 10);
4. the number of items per testlet (4, 6, 8); and
5. the number of examinees (1000, 2000).

The parameters used to generate data from the GT Model were loosely based off of Li et al. (2006): Examinee abilities (θ_j) and testlet effects (γ_{dj}) were drawn from a $N(0,1)$ distribution; item discrimination parameters (α_{i1}, α_{i2}) were drawn from a $LN(-.5, 25)$ distribution; and item difficulty parameters were drawn from a $N(0,1)$ distribution. The parameters used to generate the RLT model were similar to the GT model: Examinee abilities (θ_j) were drawn from a $N(0,1)$ distribution; the testlet slope effect (δ_{dj}) was drawn from a $N(0, .5)$ distribution; item discrimination parameters (α_i) were drawn from a $LN(-.5, 25)$ distribution; and item difficulty parameters were drawn from a $N(0,1)$ distribution. The data generating parameters for the MET model were the following: Examinee abilities (θ_j) were drawn from a

$N(0,1)$ distribution; the testlet rate parameter ω_{dj} was fixed at 2.5 (which pilot runs showed to produce a sizable testlet effect); item discrimination parameters (α_i) were drawn from a $LN(-.5, 25)$ distribution; and item difficulty parameters were drawn from a $N(0,1)$ distribution. Additionally, because the MET is a mixture model, half the examinees belonged to a group that were affected by item sequence and the other half were not. A total of 20 datasets were generated from each cell in the factorial design.

We used stochastic methods for parameter estimation and explored the posterior distributions through a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm with metropolis-hasting steps programmed in C. We ran six chains of 50,000 iterations that were thinned by a factor of 5. The first 3,000 iterations tuned the sampler and the 3,500 iterations that followed were treated as burn-ins and discarded. In addition to randomly examining parameter trace plots, we assessed convergence with the \hat{R} criterion (Brooks & Gelman, 1998) and roughly all the estimated parameters had values less than 1.1, indicating the chains converged. Unless constrained, we used uninformative priors for all parameters. Specifically, ability distributions and the testlet effects were constrained to a $N(0,1)$ distribution, whereas uninformed priors were used for item discrimination, $LN(0,2)$, item difficulties $N(0,5)$, testlet slope effect $N(0, 5)$, testlet rate parameter, $N(0,10)$, and the group membership indicator in the MET $Bern(.5)$.

To assess data fit, we investigate the root mean square error (RMSE) of the maximum a posterior parameter estimates to their true values. The means for each cell in the design are displayed in Table 1 (six testlet exam), Table 2 (eight testlet exam), and Table 3 (ten testlet exam).

Table 1
Parameter recovery (RMSE) for a 6 Testlet exam as a function of number of items per testlet and sample size

Model Parameter	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
Theta	0.54	0.51	0.43	0.55	0.50	0.41
Item Difficulty	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.06
Item Discrimination	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05
Item Discrimination (Testlet)	0.14	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08
Gamma (Testlet)	0.77	0.71	0.70	0.80	0.78	0.75
Random Linear Testlet						
Theta	0.54	0.47	0.44	0.58	0.45	0.42
Item Difficulty	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.05
Item Discrimination	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.04
Delta (Testlet Slope)	0.45	0.37	0.31	0.42	0.36	0.32
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
Theta	0.61	0.58	0.52	0.60	0.55	0.54
Item Difficulty	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06
Item Discrimination	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06
Omega (Testlet Rate)	0.68	0.62	0.61	0.75	0.73	0.72
Group Membership*	0.83	0.84	0.85	0.73	0.77	0.76

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified

Table 2
Parameter recovery (RMSE) for 8 Testlet exams as a function of number of items per testlet and sample size

Model Parameter	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
Theta	0.53	0.51	0.43	0.54	0.50	0.44
Item Difficulty	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.04
Item Discrimination	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.04
Item Discrimination (Testlet)	0.14	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.10	0.08
Gamma (Testlet)	0.78	0.68	0.67	0.80	0.75	0.77
Random Linear Testlet						
Theta	0.55	0.47	0.43	0.55	0.46	0.41
Item Difficulty	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.05
Item Discrimination	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.05	0.05
Delta (Testlet Slope)	0.41	0.37	0.29	0.40	0.34	0.28
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
Theta	0.55	0.51	0.49	0.53	0.49	0.51
Item Difficulty	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.04
Item Discrimination	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.04
Omega (Testlet Rate)	0.19	0.14	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.08
Group Membership*	0.82	0.86	0.87	0.81	0.79	0.88

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified

Table 3
Parameter recovery (RMSE) for 10 Testlet exams as a function of number of items per testlet and sample size

Model Parameter	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
Theta	0.49	0.44	0.39	0.51	0.49	0.41
Item Difficulty	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.04
Item Discrimination	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05
Item Discrimination (Testlet)	0.15	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.08
Gamma (Testlet)	0.77	0.68	0.66	0.79	0.77	0.75
Random Linear Testlet						
Theta	0.50	0.46	0.41	0.48	0.41	0.35
Item Difficulty	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.05
Item Discrimination	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.05
Delta (Testlet Slope)	0.41	0.35	0.29	0.37	0.29	0.27
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
Theta	0.55	0.51	0.49	0.51	0.47	0.42
Item Difficulty	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.06
Item Discrimination	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.05
Omega (Testlet Rate)	0.17	0.15	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.08
Group Membership*	0.83	0.84	0.88	0.84	0.82	0.88

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified

As expected, RMSE decreases for examinee parameters as the length of the exam increases, either manifested through more testlets or more items per testlet. However, increasing the number of examinees yielded only slightly lower RMSEs for item parameters. The lack of reduction in RMSE is, in part, due to the MCMC error associated with chains of this length. Collectively, all models captured their data well with the large sample sizes used in this simulation.

Turning to model-criticism, the Bayes Factor (BF; Jeffreys, 1961; Kass & Raftery, 1995) is the classic criterion under a Bayesian framework. This relies on model comparison like the likelihood ratio test. A BF quantifies the relative amount of evidence provided by the data for two (or more) competing models and is typically expressed as the ratio of two normalized constants. This latter fact distinguishes between MCMC methods for parameter estimation and MCMC methods for calculating BFs (e.g., transdimensional MCMC; Carlin & Chib, 1995). When comparing two models \mathcal{M}_0 and \mathcal{M}_1 , the BF, \mathcal{B}_{01} is given by

$$\mathcal{B}_{01} = \frac{\int_{\theta \in \Theta_0} \text{Pr}(\text{Data} | \mathcal{M}_0, \theta) \pi_0(\theta) d\theta}{\int_{\theta \in \Theta_1} \text{Pr}(\text{Data} | \mathcal{M}_1, \theta) \pi_1(\theta) d\theta}, \quad (5)$$

where Θ_0 and Θ_1 are the parameter spaces for their respective models, and π_0 and π_1 are the prior probability density functions of the parameters for their respective models. Because a prior probability is required to calculate a BF, its choice receives much controversy. In addition to the careful selection of priors, calculating proper BFs for high-dimensional models and models that differ in dimensionality (e.g., mixture and latent class models) are particularly challenging. For this reason, Gelfand, Dey, & Chang, (1992) promoted the use of an alternative method of approximating the marginal likelihood of a model—calculating the conditional predictive ordinate (CPO) by taking the harmonic mean of the MCMC samples. The CPO is calculated for all responses by

$$CPO_{ij} = \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{f(y_{ij} | \Theta_k)} \right\}^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

where N is the total number of retained MCMC samples and Θ_k representing the parameter space at MCMC sample k . The product of the CPOs approximates a model's likelihood, and the ratio of this value for two models is the pseudo-Bayes Factor (PsBF). The main interest of this study is to determine whether the PsBF is an informative model selection criterion for establishing the true data-generating model. Tables 4 (six testlet exam), 5 (eight testlet exam), and 6 (ten testlet exam) display the results of the log PsBF.

Table 4
Model Comparison using average Pseudo-Bayes Factor Log(PsBF) for 6 testlet exams

True Model Fitted Model	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
GT vs RLT	332.56	1141.22	2257.08	629.67	2202.26	4590.37
GT vs MET	180.53	385.90	590.82	319.06	710.03	1209.58
MET vs RLT	149.98	746.06	1669.35	297.22	1489.01	3387.76
Random Linear Testlet						
RLT vs GT	173.27	924.32	2435.05	300.49	1706.61	4528.78
RLT vs MET	110.48	779.05	2484.74	200.71	1521.23	4906.17
MET vs GT	62.79	145.26	-49.69	99.78	185.38	-377.39
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
MET vs GT	37.46	66.50	113.42	59.91	109.96	169.43
MET vs RLT	10.35	448.22	1250.94	82.80	983.64	2495.59
GT vs RLT	-2.16	396.92	1136.57	30.55	874.19	2343.77

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified
 GT = General Testlet; RLT = Random Linear Testlet; MET = Mixture Exponential Testlet

Table 5
Model Comparison using average Pseudo-Bayes Factor Log(PsBF) for 8 testlet exams

True Model Fitted Model	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
GT vs RLT	455.34	1527.91	3085.38	884.59	3047.01	6278.50
GT vs MET	246.37	516.38	846.82	572.63	1013.62	1718.22
MET vs RLT	208.53	986.66	2257.03	313.95	2043.96	4578.25
Random Linear Testlet						
RLT vs GT	240.71	1219.25	3264.48	409.42	2274.28	6167.36
RLT vs MET	153.31	1025.45	3353.59	283.28	2001.72	6570.99
MET vs GT	87.40	186.58	-67.84	134.68	245.77	-444.36
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
MET vs GT	38.68	90.46	150.95	72.10	130.44	224.28
MET vs RLT	32.65	612.08	1640.07	113.40	1239.75	3399.35
GT vs RLT	1.58	534.97	1552.65	34.28	1119.60	3151.49

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified
 GT = General Testlet; RLT = Random Linear Testlet; MET = Mixture Exponential Testlet

Table 6
 Model Comparison using average Pseudo-Bayes Factor Log(PsBF) for 10 testlet exams

True Model Fitted Model	Sample Size: 1,000			Sample Size: 2,000		
	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet	4 Items Per Testlet	6 Items Per Testlet	8 Items Per Testlet
General Testlet						
GT vs RLT	557.59	1919.90	3909.74	1130.76	3779.54	7798.70
GT vs MET	295.14	675.62	1097.67	628.03	1270.82	2058.80
MET vs RLT	239.12	1236.98	2805.96	545.52	2526.21	5711.69
Random Linear Testlet						
RLT vs GT	312.97	1565.13	4138.77	511.10	2982.64	7765.63
RLT vs MET	208.10	1157.00	4195.00	340.64	2622.50	8289.19
MET vs GT	101.16	240.00	-83.00	168.28	328.96	-568.94
Mixture Exponential Testlet						
MET vs GT	52.20	110.49	118.93	81.22	147.31	148.35
MET vs RLT	23.36	757.94	2021.57	135.76	1557.65	4248.40
GT vs RLT	5.29	671.83	1863.88	41.10	1363.22	3983.08

Note. Group Membership is the average proportion of examinees accurately classified
 GT = General Testlet; RLT = Random Linear Testlet; MET = Mixture Exponential Testlet

The PsBF was a reliable criterion for model selection for practically all datasets. When the data were generated by the GT model, the PsBF showed strong support for the correct model. Additionally, this pattern maintained for the RLT generated data, which showed strong support for its model. Finally, although the PsBF consistently chose the correct model for the MET data, the amount of evidence in favor of the true model was not as substantial as for the true models in the other datasets. In conclusion, the two new sequential testlet models proposed here (RLT and MET) both capture their data reasonably. Furthermore, the PsBF is a successful criterion for distinguishing between competing testlet models for the sample sizes used in this study.

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